

VANTAA

CLIMATE-NEUTRAL BY 2030

The City of Vantaa, in Finland, is situated in Helsinki-Uusimaa region and it is characterised by a humid continental climate (Dfb).

With 240.35 square km, Vantaa counts a population of 242,819 (2022), with expected growth for the next decades.

LEADING ECONOMIC SECTORS IN VANTAA:

INDUSTRY

TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS

WHOLESALE AND RETAIL

MAIN SOURCES OF CO₂ EMISSIONS (2022):

HEATING

TRANSPORT

ELECTRICITY GENERATION

INDUSTRY

URBAN WASTE MANAGEMENT

AGRICULTURE

MAIN SOURCES OF ENERGY GENERATED IN 2023:

WASTE

BIOFUELS

COAL

MOBILITY PATTERNS:

AROUND 70% OWNS A CAR, AND 55% CHOSE SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY

SNAPSHOT OF VANTAA ON CAPACITY BUILDING:

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

Governance and Policy
Social Innovation

KEY AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT:

Finance
Implementation and technology

TOPICS OF INTEREST:

PCED energy balance and emissions calculation
District heating networks
Public-Private-Partnerships
Adaptation in built environment

Funded by
the European Union

NATIONAL LEVEL:

FINNISH CLIMATE ACT (2022) ENFORCES COORDINATION ACROSS LEVELS OF GOVERNMENT

IN VANTAA:

CLIMATE INSTITUTIONAL ROLES ACROSS DEPARTMENTS

GOVERNANCE AND POLICY

In Finland, the key pillar of climate policy is the National Climate Act. The New Climate Act (2022) sets new emission reduction targets for 2030, 2040 and 2050 in alignment with the EU and coordinates the climate policy planning system across all levels of government.

The City of Vantaa defines the local climate plans with the contribution of all relevant departments and subsidiary companies, covering the following areas of expertise: Urban development and land use planning; Environment and biodiversity; Energy; Transport, mobility and infrastructure; and Economic Development. Climate roles and responsibilities are shared across the staff and departments, contributing to a good level of coordination on ongoing initiatives and projects. Nonetheless, the sharing of information and data across departments and staff could always be improved.

The municipality also engages with the local stakeholders to discuss and implement the city climate agenda. This co-creation with the local ecosystem of citizens and stakeholders from different sectors is achieved through different initiatives such as Panels & assemblies and Neighbourhood information events.

CROSS SECTORAL CLIMATE PLANS

COOPERATION WITH LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS

IMPLEMENTATION AND TECHNOLOGY

The city of Vantaa is prioritizing the decarbonising of its Built Environment and Transport system.

When trying to reduce carbon emissions, Vantaa encounters challenges related to the need for enhanced knowledge and skills within the industry, and in the formulation of enabling policies. The high investment costs are also a barrier to carbon emission reduction.

The city has a track record of integrating circular economy principles with climate neutrality efforts and is committed to achieving targets in renewable energy production.

While Vantaa's experience with PCEDs has been primarily at the planning level, the city recognizes the importance of involving local stakeholders for a successful implementation. Prioritising engagement with investors, the building and construction industry, and the energy supply chain is a priority to realising this implementation effectively.

CURRENT LEVEL OF COMPETENCE

CLIMATE AND ENERGY DATA COLLECTION ANALYSIS

ADAPTATION SECTORS

SOCIAL INNOVATION

The city of Vantaa actively collaborates with the local ecosystem of stakeholders, as it is recognized as a key component in achieving an inclusive transition to climate neutrality.

The involvement and participation of citizens and local stakeholders are generally positive, but it varies depending on the topic and activities promoted. Participation is highly linked to the personal and sectorial interests of the stakeholders.

The main barriers identified in reaching stakeholders and citizens on climate and energy transition are a lack of awareness and capacity for participation and behavioural changes in their everyday lives. A key challenge is faced when approaching vulnerable populations. Yet it is an essential need for a fair transition.

To ensure a just transition, the city strives to include multiple perspectives, from attentiveness to gender equality, multicultural representation and intergenerational dialogue with active engagement through councils, public meetings and workshops, social media engagement and more.

To improve its social engagement capacity, the city of Vantaa is looking to innovate in the following areas:

POLICY INNOVATION

ACCESS TO SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC STATISTICAL INFORMATION AND DATA

SKILLS AND RESOURCES TO PROMOTE CLIMATE ACTION WITH RESIDENTS

PARTNERSHIPS AND COLLABORATION WITH INTERMEDIARY LOCAL ORGANISATIONS

LOCAL ENERGY RENEWABLE PRODUCTION

COLLABORATION

NEUTRALPATH key target sectors for the PCEDs implementation are: Built Environment, Energy and Mobility

FINANCING AND BUSINESS MODELS FOR PCEDS AND CLIMATE NEUTRALITY

The city of Vantaa possesses a solid background in energy efficiency and investment planning, leveraging tools like revolving funds and funding support from financial institutions, alongside innovative financing schemes like Energy Performance Contracting.

The city of Vantaa is actively seeking to enhance its understanding of comprehensive financial planning, covering actions, impacts, and benefits. There is a specific interest in further developing financial knowledge and know-how. A significant priority includes acquiring experience in defining and implementing business models specifically tailored for energy efficiency-related projects.

Regarding financing capacity for climate neutrality, Vantaa is set to inaugurate the Climate Budget Pilot in 2024. This initiative spans various domains of climate action, encompassing mitigation, adaptation, circular economy, green mobility, renewables, and energy efficiency.

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

- Revolving funds
- Funding from financing institutions
- Energy Performance Contracting (EPC)

INTERESTED IN LEARNING ABOUT:

- Climate action investment planning and funding opportunities
- Private climate investments in the city area

The Capacity Building Program will support the upskilling of public authorities and local communities across these key cross-cutting areas and the Key Target Sectors to enable successful PCED implementation and unlock the systemic transformation necessary to achieve climate neutrality.

If you want to know more:

[Committed Vantaa Program](#)

[Vantaa's Roadmap to Resource Wisdom](#)

[Participatory Vantaa Digital Platform](#)

neutralpath.eu/

2030
NEUTRALPATH

Funded by
the European Union